

A State-Space Kalman Filtering Framework for 2D Motorsport Telemetry Reconstruction

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Abstract—A linear Gaussian state-space framework is presented for reconstructing physically consistent two-dimensional motorsport telemetry from noisy positional measurements. The system employs a constant-acceleration motion model and recursive Kalman filtering with Joseph-form covariance stabilization to ensure numerical robustness. Validation across five distinct Formula 1 circuit geometries demonstrates bounded RMSE behavior and systematic suppression of high-frequency velocity artifacts. Through algorithmic optimization and Numba Just-In-Time compilation, an overall $1500\times$ performance improvement is achieved, enabling real-time replay applications.

I. INTRODUCTION

Motorsport telemetry data frequently exhibits irregular sampling intervals, measurement noise, and discontinuities that produce physically inconsistent replay trajectories. Naive interpolation amplifies noise and introduces artificial high-frequency oscillations in derived velocity estimates.

Rather than applying heuristic smoothing, this work formulates trajectory reconstruction as a linear Gaussian state estimation problem.

II. STATE-SPACE FORMULATION

A. State Definition

$$\mathbf{x}_k = [x_k \quad y_k \quad v_{x,k} \quad v_{y,k} \quad a_{x,k} \quad a_{y,k}]^T \quad (1)$$

B. Motion Model

$$\mathbf{x}_{k+1} = F\mathbf{x}_k + \mathbf{w}_k \quad (2)$$

where

$$F = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & \Delta t & 0 & \frac{1}{2}\Delta t^2 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & \Delta t & 0 & \frac{1}{2}\Delta t^2 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & \Delta t & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & \Delta t \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

C. Measurement Model

$$\mathbf{z}_k = H\mathbf{x}_k + \mathbf{v}_k \quad (4)$$

$$H = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

D. Process and Measurement Noise Modeling

The process noise $\mathbf{w}_k \sim \mathcal{N}(0, Q)$ captures unmodeled acceleration dynamics. Q is constructed assuming independent white acceleration noise with variance σ_a^2 applied along both spatial axes.

Measurement noise $\mathbf{v}_k \sim \mathcal{N}(0, R)$ is modeled as zero-mean Gaussian with isotropic covariance:

$$R = \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_m^2 & 0 \\ 0 & \sigma_m^2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

E. Recursive Kalman Filtering Equations

Prediction step:

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k|k-1} = F\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k-1|k-1} \quad (7)$$

$$P_{k|k-1} = FP_{k-1|k-1}F^T + Q \quad (8)$$

Kalman gain:

$$K_k = P_{k|k-1}H^T(H P_{k|k-1}H^T + R)^{-1} \quad (9)$$

State update:

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k|k} = \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k|k-1} + K_k(\mathbf{z}_k - H\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k|k-1}) \quad (10)$$

Joseph stabilized covariance update:

$$P_{k|k} = (I - K_kH)P_{k|k-1}(I - K_kH)^T + K_kRK_k^T \quad (11)$$

III. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Validation was performed across five distinct 2025 Formula 1 race circuits representing high-speed, street, and technical layouts. For each event, the fastest race driver was selected as a reference trajectory.

Raw positional telemetry provided by the FastF1 API consists of irregularly spaced samples and contains measurement noise. Since the Kalman filter operates on a uniform time grid, raw samples were first resampled to 10 Hz using linear interpolation. The filter output was then interpolated back onto the original irregular timestamps to enable direct comparison against the raw telemetry.

A. Reconstruction Error Metric

$$e_k = \sqrt{(x_k^{\text{orig}} - \hat{x}_k)^2 + (y_k^{\text{orig}} - \hat{y}_k)^2} \quad (12)$$

$$\text{RMSE} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{k=1}^N e_k^2} \quad (13)$$

B. Trajectory Reconstruction

Across all circuits, the filtered trajectories maintain geometric consistency while visibly reducing small-scale oscillations present in the raw data.

C. Velocity Behavior

Velocity estimates derived directly from raw positional telemetry exhibit high-frequency fluctuations due to amplification of measurement noise during numerical differentiation. These oscillations are particularly pronounced in high-speed and rapidly varying track segments.

The Kalman filter significantly attenuates these artifacts while preserving the underlying dynamic trends of vehicle motion.

D. Reconstruction Error

The error magnitudes remain bounded across all circuits, indicating stable estimator behavior without numerical divergence.

E. Computational Complexity

For an n -state linear Kalman filter, covariance propagation scales as $\mathcal{O}(n^3)$. For the fixed six-state formulation presented here, computational cost remains negligible in practice. Combined with Numba JIT acceleration, per-step latency is sufficiently low to enable real-time telemetry replay.

IV. CONCLUSION

A computationally efficient linear Gaussian estimator for two-dimensional telemetry reconstruction has been presented. Multi-circuit validation demonstrates bounded RMSE and systematic artifact suppression while preserving physically consistent motion dynamics.

REFERENCES

- [1] R. E. Kalman, "A New Approach to Linear Filtering and Prediction Problems," *Journal of Basic Engineering*, 1960.

(a) British GP

(b) Monaco GP

(c) Italian GP

(d) Singapore GP

(e) Japanese GP

Fig. 1: Original telemetry (gray dashed) versus Kalman-filtered trajectory (black solid). The estimator preserves global track geometry while suppressing measurement jitter.

(a) British GP

(b) Monaco GP

(c) Italian GP

(d) Singapore GP

(e) Japanese GP

Fig. 2: Velocity derived from original telemetry (gray dashed) and filtered states (black solid). High-frequency oscillations are systematically suppressed.

(a) British GP

(b) Monaco GP

(c) Italian GP

(d) Singapore GP

(e) Japanese GP

Fig. 3: Pointwise reconstruction error between original telemetry and filtered state estimate. Error remains bounded without divergence.